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Alkali-doped polyvinyl alcohol – polybenzimidazole membranes for alkaline water electrolysis

L. A. Diaz^a, R. E. Coppola^a, G. C. Abuin^{a,*}, R. Escudero-Cid^b, D. Herranz^b, P. Ocón^b

^aInstituto Nacional de Tecnología Industrial (INTI), Centro de Procesos Superficiales, Av. General Paz 5445, B1650KNA, San Martín, Buenos Aires, Argentina

^bUniversidad Autónoma de Madrid, Departamento de Química Física Aplicada, C/Francisco Tomás y Valiente 7, 28049, Madrid, Spain UAM

*Corresponding author. gabuin@inti.gob.ar

Abstract

We developed an innovative polymer blend system composed of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and polybenzimidazole as an anionic membrane for application to zero gap alkaline electrolyzers. The challenge was to combine PVA with either poly[2-2'-(m-phenylene)-5-5'-bibenzimidazole] (PBI) or poly (2,5-benzimidazole) (ABPBI) to complement these neutral polymers, which must be doped to conduct, with hydroxyl groups that benefit the OH⁻ transport mechanism. We studied PVA-PBI and PVA-ABPBI membranes with compositions varying between 2:1 and 8:1, with 4:1 being best ratio. PVA is crosslinked inside PVA-PBI 4:1 and PVA-ABPBI 4:1 membranes with glutaraldehyde (GA) by immersion in a reaction solution with different GA contents ranging from 0.5 vol. % to 50 vol. % to enhance the stability of the membranes. The chemical stability in a KOH environment, thermal and mechanical properties, surface morphology, swelling, water / KOH sorption, and conductivity of the linear alkali-doped (L-PVA-PBI, L-PVA-ABPBI) and crosslinked (C-PVA-PBI, C-PVA-ABPBI) membranes were analysed. The best results were observed for the C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 membrane crosslinked in 0.5 vol. % GA, which exhibited specific conductivities at 90 °C of 50 mS·cm⁻¹ and 90 mS·cm⁻¹ when doped using 15 wt. % and 30 wt. % KOH, respectively. In short-term electrolysis tests performed with circulated 15 wt. % KOH at 50 °C, this membrane exhibited a current density that was twice that of the commercial porous Zirfon[®] diaphragm (i.e., 300 mA·cm⁻² and 140 mA·cm⁻², respectively) at a cell voltage of 2.0 V. The performance achieved with the C-PVA-ABPBI membrane in a 15 wt. % KOH electrolyte at 70 °C was good (i.e., 360 mA·cm⁻² at a cell voltage of 1.9 V).

Keywords: Anion exchange membranes; PVA; PBI; ABPBI; water electrolysis.

1 Introduction

Hydrogen is a viable energy carrier for renewable and sustainable energy and a promising energy conversion technology for intermittent electricity generation from solar cells and windmills. Water electrolysis (WE) is an advantageous process for the production of pure hydrogen that must reduce investment and operational costs to achieve a widespread utilization. The currently employed technologies include proton exchange membrane WE (PEMWE) and liquid alkaline WE (LAWE). LAWE is a well-established technology that consists of nickel electrodes separated by a porous diaphragm and employs a liquid electrolyte (i.e., typically 30 wt. % KOH) at 80-90 °C. Although harmful to the materials, the high temperature and electrolyte concentration result in a decrease in the ohmic drop in the cell, which can be operated at voltages ranging from 1.9 to 2.1 V [1–4].

A comparison of the LAWE and PEMWE technologies indicates that PEMWE is advantageous in terms of the electrochemical performance. In addition, LAWE is advantageous in terms of cost savings because PEMWE employs precious metals as catalysts. The zero gap configuration with the porous electrodes attached to an anion-selective membrane, which is also an anion-exchange membrane (AEM), can be a good intermediate alternative. In zero gap cells, the porous electrodes are in contact with both sides of the AEM, reducing the voltage drop as well as the energy requirement for H₂ production. Furthermore, the replacement of the diaphragm and electrolyte-filled gap of LAWE by an ion-conducting membrane allows for a significant reduction in the electrolyte concentration, resulting in a reduction in the corrosive stress of the material in the system and auxiliary devices [4]. The main challenge of this alternative is to identify an anion selective membrane with a satisfactory ionic conductivity as well as sufficient chemical stability under the strongly alkaline environments and elevated temperatures that are employed in these devices. Currently, the operational temperature of an anion-selective membrane is limited to a temperature below 70 °C due to the chemical stability of the functional groups [1]. In fact, an anion-selective membrane capable of achieving low ohmic drops at moderate temperatures and KOH concentrations would be advantageous for avoiding the use of an aggressive media (e.g., concentrated KOH) at high temperatures.

Many studies have focused on the application of AEMs to fuel cells, especially direct alcohol fuel cells. As proposed by Merle et al., AEMs can be categorized as *heterogeneous membranes*, which are composed of an anion solvating polymer matrix doped with an alkaline hydroxide solution; or *homogeneous membranes*, which are composed of an anion-exchanging polymer [5].

Polymers modified by incorporation of quaternary ammonium groups account for most of the studied homogeneous AEMs [6–8]. These AEMs exhibit good performance in terms of thermochemical stability and conductivity but they suffer from chemical degradation by hydroxide anions that attack the quaternary ammonium groups, progressively reducing their ion-exchange capacity [9].

This problem is avoided in heterogeneous membranes where the anion transport does not depend on functional groups but on the alkali doping solution. Alkali-doped PBI poly[2,2'-(m-phenylene)-5,5'-bibenzimidazole] and PBI-modified polymers are well known materials that are characterized by satisfactory thermochemical and mechanical properties. PBI and ABPBI doped with H_3PO_4 (PA) have been broadly evaluated in PEM fuel cells that were fed with H_2 or alcohol and operated up to 180 °C for high-temperature PEM fuel cells (HT-PEMFC) [10,11]. To a smaller extent, KOH-doped polybenzimidazole membranes have also been evaluated for use in fuel cells. For these membranes, Xing and Savadogo [12] reported room temperature ionic conductivities (IC) of $5 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ to $20 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ in H_2 fuel cells. Additional studies have also evaluated this type of membrane in hydrogen and direct alcohol fuel cells [13–16].

For LAWE applications, Aili et al. reported an IC of $20 \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ for 3 M KOH-doped PBI membranes at room temperature [17]. When doped in 30 wt. % KOH, the crosslinked PBI membranes exhibited better stability than the linear ones in durability tests performed at 85 °C. We reported similar conductivities and promising performances in a zero gap LAWE device with linear and benzoxazine-crosslinked ABPBI membranes [18].

Recently, research efforts have been focused on systemically characterizing the physicochemical properties of polybenzimidazole in alkaline environments. Zeng et al. [19] studied PBI membranes equilibrated in KOH (0 – 6 M) and proposed a mechanism for the interaction between the doped alkali and the polymer. Aili et al. [20] employed a combination of techniques

to study the physicochemical properties of PBI films in aqueous KOH with concentrations ranging from 0 to 50 wt. %. Furthermore, Kraglund et al. [21] investigated the influence of the electrolyte concentration on the performance and stability of a PBI membrane in a zero gap alkaline water electrolyser.

Herein, we combined PBI and ABPBI polymers with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). This polyhydroxyl polymer (PVA) has a film forming ability and is inexpensive, biodegradable and thermochemically stable. PVA also possesses a good OH⁻ transport ability based on the hydrophilicity derived from the presence of a considerable number of hydroxyl group pendants on its backbone. In addition, its structure becomes amorphous upon incorporation of KOH, being ionic conductivity mainly localized in the amorphous phase [22]. Some studies have investigated PVA as an anion solvating polymer in pure PVA, blend or composite membranes [5,22].

In the current study, we performed a comparative study of new membranes based on a blend of PBI or ABPBI and PVA. These membranes are interesting for WE applications because PBI / ABPBI have good thermal and mechanical properties, and PVA could contribute to important improvements in conductivity. The aim of this study was to characterize the properties and electrochemical performance of alkali-doped PVA-PBI and PVA-ABPBI membranes in a zero gap electrolyser cell.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

3,4-Diaminobenzoic acid (DABA, 97 wt. %), polyphosphoric acid (PPA, 85 wt. %, Aldrich), PBI powder (BETWEEN, LizenzGMBH), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA, hydrolysed powder with a MW of 89,000-98,000, 99+ %, Aldrich), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 99.9 %, Aldrich), N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAc, 99.5 %, Aldrich), glutaraldehyde (GA, 25 % aqueous solution, Aldrich), potassium hydroxide (KOH, 85 wt. %, Aldrich), H₂SO₄ (96 wt. %, Baker Analysed), HCl (35 – 36 wt. %, Biopack) and ethanol (Merck) were employed in this study. Deionized water was used to prepare the aqueous solutions.

The chemical structures of the PBI, ABPBI and PVA polymers are shown in Figure 1. The ABPBI polymer was prepared by condensation of the DABA monomer in PPA followed by neutralization, washing, drying and milling according to a previously reported procedure [18]. The intrinsic viscosity of the polymer solution in 96 wt. % H_2SO_4 at 30 °C was $2.96 \text{ dl}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, and the averaged molecular weight, which was calculated from the Mark–Houwink equation [23], was $23,200 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of the PBI, ABPBI, linear PVA and PVA crosslinked with glutaraldehyde.

2.2 Membrane preparation

The L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-ABPBI membranes were synthesized using a casting method. A solution of 5 wt. % PVA in DMSO was obtained by heating at 85 °C for 30 minutes under continuous stirring (1 g of PVA in 20 g of DMSO). 3.5 wt. % PBI in DMAc was obtained by heating at 80 °C for 48 hours (3.5 g of PBI in 96.5 g of DMAc). For the L-PVA-PBI membranes,

the appropriate amounts of the PVA/DMSO and PBI/DMAc solutions were transferred to a glass beaker according to the required molar ratio (e.g., 2:1). The mixtures were stirred for 40 minutes at 500 rpm, placed in Petri dishes coated with a PTFE liner and introduced into a vacuum oven (Memert VO200), where the pressure was lowered from room pressure to 10 mbar. During the entire casting process, the temperature was maintained at 40 °C. Then, the membranes were easily peeled off the PTFE liner and stored in inert plastic bags prior to use.

For the L-PVA-ABPBI membranes, 1 wt. % PVA in DMSO was prepared by heating at 80 °C for 30 minutes under continuous stirring (1 g of PVA in 100 g in DMSO), and then, the solution was cooled to room temperature. ABPBI was dissolved in absolute ethanol/NaOH according to a previously reported procedure [11]. The ethanol solution contained ca. 1 wt. % ABPBI, and 1 wt. % NaOH was added for dissolution of ABPBI. The mixture was refluxed at 50 °C until complete dissolution of ABPBI was achieved.

Based on the desired proportion of L-PVA-ABPBI, the prepared solutions PVA/DMSO and ABPBI/NaOH/ethanol (i.e., amounts corresponding to the desired molar proportion (e.g., 2:1) were transferred to a glass beaker and gently stirred. Then, the solutions were placed in Petri dishes in an air convection oven (San Jor SE60DF) overnight at 50 °C. Finally, the membranes were removed by immersing them in water and stored in inert plastic bags prior to use.

The C-PVA-PBI and C-PVA-ABPBI crosslinked membranes were prepared according to the procedure reported by Yeom et al. [24]. The dry L-PVA-PBI or L-PVA-ABPBI membrane was heated at 40 °C for 48 h in different reaction solutions containing different amounts the aqueous GA solution, acetone and HCl. The GA solution content in the reaction solution ranged from 0.5 vol. % to 50 vol. %. The HCl content was maintained at 0.12 vol. %. After the process, the membrane was washed several times with DI water and placed in pure water for 24 h at 40 °C to remove any residual HCl and GA followed by drying in an oven overnight at 50 °C.

The L-PVA and L-ABPBI membranes were prepared by casting from solutions containing 1 wt. % PVA in DMSO and ABPBI in ethanol/NaOH, respectively. When necessary, the L-PVA and L-ABPBI membranes were subjected to treatment with GA according to the previously described procedure.

For all samples, the membrane thickness ranged from 40 μm to 120 μm (measured with a Mitutoyo Digital Micrometer). The linear and crosslinked PBI and ABPBI membranes were doped in KOH solutions at room temperature.

2.3 Alkaline water electrolysis

A single-cell laboratory water electrolyser with a zero gap configuration [18] was used to test the linear and crosslinked PVA-ABPBI and PVA-PBI membranes. Two 3.61 cm^2 electrodes consisting of Ni foam (Sigma Aldrich, thickness 1.6 mm, bulk density 0.45 g/cm^3 , porosity 95 %) were directly attached to the membrane surfaces. The active electrode surface area was 4.4 cm^2 in this arrangement. The single cell was fabricated from gold-plated Ni sheets, which were used as current collectors and electrolyte distributors. The cell was inserted in the system as described in [18], and KOH solution was recirculated by a dual head pump. The electrolysis load curves were measured using a cell voltage that ranged from 1.5 V to 2.0 V at 50 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 70 $^\circ\text{C}$. In the chronopotentiometric measurements, a constant current density of 200 mA cm^{-2} was applied for 60 min.

2.4 Characterization of crosslinking reactions

Infrared spectroscopy was performed using an FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Scientific Nicolet 6700 FTIR). The IR spectra were recorded for non-doped crosslinked C-PVA-PBI and C-PVA-ABPBI samples to detect changes in the different GA amounts in the crosslinking reaction solution.

In order to assess the crosslinking of the membrane, the gel content test was performed. A weighted sample of membrane was immersed in a DMSO-Ethanol 5:2, with 1 wt. % NaOH, at 80 $^\circ\text{C}$. After certain periods of time, the sample was removed, washed, dried and weighted. The ratio of the residual (not dissolved) mass relative to the initial mass of the sample, was identified as the gel fraction, indicative of crosslinking of the membrane.

2.5 Stability in alkaline environment, surface morphology, mechanical and thermal properties

The membrane stability was evaluated in an alkaline environment. The membrane samples were immersed for 7 days in KOH solutions with concentrations ranging from 15 wt. % to 30 wt. % at 70 °C.

The surface morphology analysis was performed using a FEI QUANTA 250 scanning electron microscope (SEM) on membrane samples sputter coated with Au.

The thermal properties of the linear and crosslinked membranes were studied by thermogravimetric analysis (TG) on a TA Instrument 20. The samples were heated to 900° C at a heating rate of 10° C·min⁻¹ under a nitrogen atmosphere. The weight loss was measured and reported as a function of the temperature. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed to investigate the miscibility behaviour of PVA and polybenzimidazole polymers based on analysis of the glass transition temperatures. DSC was measured in a TA Instrument 10, under nitrogen atmosphere doing a heating procedure from -90 to 500 °C at a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ with the samples sealed in aluminium pans.

The mechanical properties were measured with an INSTRON model 3345 testing instrument, at 65 % RH and room temperature. The membrane samples, with length 40 mm and width 4 mm, doped in 15 wt. % KOH, were pulled at a crosshead speed of 5 mm min⁻¹.

2.6 Swelling, KOH doping level and water sorption

The membrane swelling was calculated based in the thickness, length and width before and after doping of the dry membrane.

The KOH doping level and water content were determined using the following method. Non-doped membrane samples were dried for 12 hours at 80 °C under vacuum, weighed to determine the dry weight (w_0), and immersed in a 15 wt. % KOH solution. After 7 days, each membrane was removed from the doping solution, and its surface was dried with tissue paper. Next, the

sample was weight to obtain the wet weight of the sample (w_s). Then, the samples were dried overnight at 80 °C under vacuum and weighed again (w_d). This weight (w_d) was equivalent to weight of the polymer and KOH, and the water content (w_w) was determined to be $w_w = w_s - w_d$. In addition, the KOH content (w_a) was obtained as follows: $w_a = w_d - w_0$.

Finally, to determine if any polymer was lost in the doping solution, the samples were washed several times in water at 70 °C, dried overnight at 80 °C under vacuum and weighed again. If this weight equals w_0 , no polymer loss occurs during the doping process. However, if any polymer loss was observed, it is necessary to determine if this loss occurs during doping or during the washing process.

The IR spectra were employed to determinate the possible PVA dissolution from the membranes during the doping process. For this purpose, PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes were added to 15 wt. % KOH for 7 days in stainless steel vessels to avoid organic contamination of the solutions from plastic vessels. After removal of the membrane, the doping solution was neutralized with HCl, and the resulting salt solution was heated at 80 °C until dried. Then, 40 ml of ethanol was added to dissolve the PVA. The mixture was placed in a spin dryer at 500 rpm. Finally, a 10 ml aliquot of the supernatant was transferred to an aluminium container and dried. The infrared spectrum of the resulting solid was recorded.

2.7 Ionic conductivity

The through plane ionic conductivity (σ) of the membranes was determined based on a complex impedance analysis (EIS) in a temperature range from 25 °C to 110 °C. A two-point technique was employed where two stainless steel electrodes were placed in contact with opposite sides of the membrane sample. The samples were introduced to the conductivity cell under wet conditions, and the conductivity measurement was performed immediately. The EIS measurements were carried out with an Autolab PGSTAT 30N coupled to a frequency response analyser (FRA). The frequencies were swept from 100 kHz to 1 Hz, and six points per decade were recorded with an AC signal amplitude of 10 mV around the open circuit potential. Each membrane sample was washed in DI water to remove the excess KOH solution, dried carefully

with tissue paper and sandwiched between two stainless steel electrodes. The membrane conductivity was obtained from the resistance measurement (R) from the intercept of the real axis of the Nyquist plot at high frequencies.

The specific ionic conductivity was calculated as follows:

$$\sigma = \frac{\delta}{RA} \quad (1)$$

where δ (cm) is the thickness of the membrane and A (cm²) is the active surface area of the sample (0.36 cm²).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Selection of PVA-polybenzimidazole ratio

L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-ABPBI with compositions varying from 2:1 to 8:1 (molar ratio) were prepared using a solution casting method, as described in section 2.2. Prior to use in the WE cell, the membranes were alkali doped by immersion in 15 wt. % KOH aqueous solutions for 7 days at room temperature.

The effect of the PVA-polybenzimidazole ratio on the properties, which will define the behaviour of these membranes in the zero gap configuration LAWE process, is difficult to predict. The LAWE performance is influenced by the membrane conductivity, mechanical properties, permeability, and contact resistance between the membrane and the Ni foam electrodes as well as other properties. Therefore, the water electrolysis experiments performed in the single-cell laboratory water electrolyser with a zero gap configuration described in section 2.3 were performed first, and based on the load curves (current – cell-potential) and chronopotentiometric results, the best PVA:PBI ratio was selected for subsequent characterizations.

The electrolysis load curves obtained for the L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-ABPBI membranes with compositions varying from 2:1 to 8:1 (15 wt. % KOH, 50 °C) are shown in Figures 2 a) and b), respectively, and the chronopotentiometric curves for the same membranes in 15 wt. % KOH at 50 °C ($i = 200 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) are shown in Figures 3 a) and 3 b), respectively. In addition, the results are summarized in Table 1. The membranes with L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-ABPBI compositions of 2:1 and 8:1 exhibited very poor performance for the electrolysis load or chronopotentiometric measurements. The membranes with PVA-PBI compositions of 4:1 and 6:1 exhibited similar good performances according to their electrolysis load curves, where the L-PVA-PBI 4:1 response in the chronopotentiometric measurements was slightly better than the response of PVA-PBI 6:1. As shown in Table 1, after 3500 s at $200 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, the cell voltage was 2.3 V for the L-PVA-PBI 4:1 membrane and 2.5 V for the L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 and L-PVA-PBI 6:1 membranes.

Table 1: Performance of laboratory electrolysis cell tested with different anion-exchange membranes with circulating 15 wt. % KOH at 50 °C.

Membrane	Current density ($\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) at cell voltage 1.95 V	Cell voltage at 3500 s, applied current density = $200 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$
L-PVA-PBI 2:1	60	4.0
L-PVA-PBI 4:1	140	2.3
L-PVA-PBI 6:1	140	2.5
L-PVA-PBI 8:1	30	4.0
L-PVA-ABPBI 2:1	30	7.1
L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1	160	2.5
L-PVA-ABPBI 6:1	80	3.4
L-PVA-ABPBI 8:1	40	4.5

In summary, L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 exhibited the best performance based on both current – potential and chronopotentiometric measurements.

Figure 2: LAWE load curves for membranes in 15 wt. % KOH at 50 °C: **a)** L-PVA-PBI membrane performance between 2:1 and 8:1. **b)** L-PVA-ABPBI membranes performance between 2:1 and 8:1.

Based in these results, a PVA:polybenzimidazole ratio of 4:1 provide the best results among the studied ratios, and therefore, the properties of L-PVA-PBI 4:1 and L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 will be evaluated. When we refer to L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-ABPBI membranes in subsequent sections, a 4:1 ratio was employed.

Figure 3: Chronopotentiometric curves for membranes in 15 wt. % KOH at 50 °C, $i=200 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^2$: **a)** L-PVA-ABPBI membranes and **b)** L-PVA-PBI membranes.

3.2 Preparation of crosslinked PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes. IR spectral analysis.

Although PVA is an advantageous polymer due to its chemical stability, film forming ability and low cost, it typically requires reinforcement via crosslinking reactions to enhance its mechanical, thermal and chemical stabilities for PEMFC / WE applications [5]. Yeom et al. [24] prepared very stable pure PVA membranes crosslinked with glutaraldehyde by immersing PVA films in acetone with different GA contents (5 to 50 vol. % aqueous solution) using HCl as the catalyst. The membrane prepared with 5 vol. % GA exhibited the best performance in the pervaporation separation of acetic acid water mixtures.

It is important to note that the crosslinking process that involves the reaction between GA molecules and hydroxyl pendant groups on the backbone of the PVA polymer can affect the hydrophilic nature of the membrane as well as hydroxyl transport in PVA-based anion conducting membranes.

The C-PVA-PBI 4:1 and C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 crosslinked membranes were prepared, as described in section 2.2, with a GA solution content ranging from 0.5 vol. % to 50 vol. %. Figures 4 a) and S1 show the IR spectra of the C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 and C-PVA-PBI 4:1 membranes, respectively. As observed for pure PVA membranes by Yeom and Lee [24], the IR spectra changed as the GA solution content increase as follows:

- (i) A decrease in the absorbance of the peak at $3300 - 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the loss of hydroxyl groups from PVA upon reaction with aldehydes (acetylation).
- (ii) An increase in the absorbance peaks located at $1720, 2731$ and 2866 cm^{-1} , which correspond to aldehyde groups. This change may be related to unreacted GA, which is unlikely due to the membranes being subjected to a several washing processes to remove residual GA. Therefore, this change must be related to monofunctional reactions of GA, where only one of the aldehyde groups of the GA molecule reacts with the PVA chain, and the other group remains unreacted and a pendant on the PVA chain. Yeom and Lee observed this effect in pure PVA membranes [24] and postulated that a monofunctional reaction is favoured when reduction in the chain mobility occurs due to the progress of the bifunctional crosslinking reaction.
- (iii) An increase in the absorbance peaks between 970 and 1385 cm^{-1} due to the formation of acetal carbon-oxygen bonds, which results from a reaction between hydroxyl and aldehyde

groups: 2 aldehyde groups from GA with hydroxyl groups from PVA (bifunctional reaction involving crosslinking) or a monofunctional reaction.

An analysis of the IR spectra was carried out to identify the changes. The absorbance ratios of the functional groups with respect to a reference peak were determined (see Figure 4 c). Based on the strategy reported by Yeom and Lee [24], the methylene stretching band at 2940 cm^{-1} was used as the reference peak. The hydroxyl group located at 3350 cm^{-1} and the aldehyde group located at 1720 cm^{-1} were associated with the acetylation and monofunctional reaction of GA, respectively, with A_{3350}/A_{2940} and A_{1720}/A_{2940} absorbance ratios for the hydroxyl and aldehyde groups, respectively. The peaks assigned to the formation of acetal carbon-oxygen bonds were not selected due to base line issues.

The results in Figure 4 b) indicate that the absorbance ratio for the hydroxyl groups decreases with increasing GA concentration in the reaction solution (acetylation reaction). However, the absorbance ratio corresponding to the monofunctional reaction increases. The trends in the absorbance ratio for the hydroxyl groups in pure PVA, PVA-PBI and PVA-ABPBI membranes are shown in Figure 4 c). The PVA and PVA-ABPBI membranes exhibit a similar trend. Although A_{3350}/A_{2940} in the PVA membrane is higher than that in the PVA-ABPBI membrane, both ratios tend to have the same constant value at GA concentrations in the reaction solution higher than 30 vol. %. The absorbance ratio for hydroxyl groups in the PVA-PBI membranes exhibits a different behaviour with the A_{3350}/A_{2940} values being considerably higher than those for the PVA and PVA-ABPBI membranes. This behaviour may be related to the polymer microstructure, which is more compact in the PVA-PBI membranes than in the PVA-ABPBI membranes. This microstructural difference between the PBI and ABPBI membranes has been previously reported [26], and the compact structure of PVA-PBI can hinder GA molecule access to hydroxide sites in PVA.

Figure 4: **a)** IR spectra of C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 membranes crosslinked in reaction solution with different GA solution contents: (a) 0 vol. % GA, (b) 0.5 vol. % GA, (c) 1 vol. % GA, (d) 5 vol. % GA, (e) 10 vol. % GA, (f) 30 vol. % GA and (g) 50 vol. % GA. **b)** A_{3350}/A_{2940} and A_{1720}/A_{2940} absorbance ratios for (○) hydroxyl and (■) aldehyde groups, respectively, in C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 membranes crosslinked in a reaction solution with different GA solution contents. **c)** A_{3350}/A_{2940} absorbance ratios for hydroxyl groups in (▲) pure PVA membrane [14], (■) C-PVA-PBI 4:1 membrane and (●) C-PVA-ABPBA 4:1 membrane.

As shown in the C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 membrane absorbance ratio curves, the primary change in the absorbance ratio occurs in the range up to 5 vol. % GA in the reaction solution, and at the lower GA concentration in the reaction solution (0.5 vol. %), a change in the A_{3350}/A_{2940} and A_{1720}/A_{2940} absorbance ratios with respect to the absorbance ratios for the linear PVA-ABPBI 4:1 membrane was observed. Although an increasing crosslinking grade can improve membrane stability, it involves compact structures and consumption of hydrophilic PVA pendant hydroxyl groups, and therefore, a conductivity loss is expected. In fact, the ionic conductivity measurements (section 3.5) indicate that the best value was obtained for C-PVA-ABPBI (GA concentrations in reaction solutions ranged from 0.5 to 5 vol. %) with 0.5 vol. % GA, and C-PVA-PBI (IR spectra shown in Figure S1) completely lost its conductivity even at this GA concentration.

The gel content test performed by immersion in a DMSO-EtOH 5:2, with 1 wt. % NaOH, at 80 °C, showed that L-PVA-ABPBI membrane dissolved completely, while C-PVA-ABPBI (GA 0.5 vol. %) had a gel fraction of 94 % after 30 hours (Figure S2). Due to the crosslinking, the C-PVA-ABPBI (GA 0.5 vol. %) membrane could not dissolve even after immersion during 30 h at 80 °C in a DMSO-EtOH solvent in which not crosslinked PVA-ABPBI membrane dissolves immediately.

Finally, because the imidazole / aldehyde reaction has been previously reported [25], we investigated the possible reaction between GA and benzimidazole by comparing the IR spectra of L-ABPBI and the same membrane subjected to the GA crosslinking procedure with 0.5 vol. % GA in the reaction solution (i.e., C-ABPBI-GA 0.5 vol. %). No differences in the IR spectra were observed (Figure S3 and Table S1), indicating that no reaction occurred between GA and benzimidazole.

3.3 Chemical stability, surface morphology, mechanical and thermal properties

After immersion for 7 days in a 15 wt. % KOH solution at 70 °C, the L-PVA-PBI membranes with 2:1 and 8:1 compositions became fragile. When the KOH concentration was increased to 18 wt. %, the L-PVA-PBI membranes (i.e., 4:1 and 6:1) exhibited the same brittle behaviour after 7 days at 70 °C. The chemical stability of the C-PVA-PBI membrane was not measured in this study due to its low conductivity values. However, the brittle behaviour was not observed for the linear or (0.5 wt. % GA) crosslinked PVA-ABPBI membranes even after immersion for 7 days in 30 wt. % KOH at 70 °C. Regarding pure membranes immersed in KOH solutions in the same conditions, L-ABPBI became fragile after immersion in KOH concentrations higher than 15 wt. %; while L-PVA and C-PVA (0.5 wt. % GA) didn't change, except for becoming a brownish colour, after immersion even in 30 wt. % KOH.

The SEM images (Figure 5a) show heterogeneities in the front and cross-section view of the L-PVA-PBI membrane, which may be due to a lack of miscibility between the polymers. In contrast, the linear and crosslinked PVA-ABPBI membranes displayed a homogeneous appearance. In Figure 5b, the heterogeneities of the L-PVA-PBI membrane with different immersion times in 15 wt. % KOH solution are compared. The rough aspect of the round-shaped

areas on the membrane immersed for 15 days softened in the membrane aged by immersion for 7 month in this solution. This behaviour may be due to polymer loss, which could be evaluated using other methods.

Figure 5: a) SEM images of surface (upper) and cross-section area (down) from: L-PVA-PBI (left), PVA-ABPBI (centre) and C-PVA-ABPBI (0.5 vol. % GA) (right) doped membranes. b) Surface SEM images of the L-PVA-PBI membranes as a function of immersion time in a 15 wt. % KOH solution: 7 months (left) and 15 days (right). c) Thermograms and its normalized DTG derivatives for 15 wt. % doped L-PVA-PBI, PVA-ABPBI, C-PVA-PBI (0.5 vol. % GA) and C-

PVA-ABPBI (0.5 vol. % GA). d) Stress-strain curves of L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI (0.5 vol. % GA) membranes.

The thermogram profiles (TG) of the L-PVA-PBI, L-PVA-ABPBI, C-PVA-PBI and C-PVA-ABPBI membranes (Figure 5c) indicate weight loss in two temperature ranges (i.e., 180-280°C and 380-518°C). The derivative TG (DTG) peak at T higher than 300 °C is primarily due to thermal decomposition of the polymer backbone. The C-PVA-PBI membrane degrades at lower temperatures than any other membranes. In the DTG profile, the C-PVA-PBI membrane exhibits an onset peak at 100 °C, which is lower than that of C-PVA-ABPBI. It is interesting to note that the “two extreme” DTG behaviours of these two membranes coincide with C-PVA-PBI and C-PVA-ABPBI being the worst and best membranes with regards to conductivity, respectively. Therefore, the conductivity loss of the C-PVA-PBI membrane may be caused by degradation.

The water sorption peaks are typically observed at approximately 100 °C. Therefore, the first peak may be attributed to water sorption. The peak between 150 °C and 250 °C was not observed in pure ABPBI doped with KOH [18], which may be due to PVA decomposition.

The four membranes exhibited sufficient thermal stability for use under WE operating conditions (50 °C - 70 °C).

Samples of L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-ABPBI (non-doped) were tested using DSC to assess the miscibility and compatibility of the systems. The data obtained from the analysis of the endothermic DSC curves, (see Figure S4), indicated the first endothermic peak, assignable to PVA glass transition temperature (T_g) located at 32.3 °C and 40.7 °C respectively. These values are close to the pristine PVA (39.1 °C) in the same experimental conditions. The second endothermic peak at about 225 °C represents the phase transition temperature (T_m) which was the same than that of pure PVA.

We don't locate any T_g coming from PBI or ABPBI, that should be located around 425-480°C. We consider that the endothermic peaks located between 250 °C and 500 °C in Figure S4 correspond to PVA decomposition. According to this measurement, L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-

ABPBI are heterogeneous blends, because a single Tg between both precursors polymers was not found.

Finally, the stress-strain curves in Figure 5d demonstrate that the crosslinking of PVA in polymer blend PVA-polybenzimidazole system enhance the mechanical properties of the membrane. C-PVA-ABPBI (0.5 vol. % GA) membrane exhibits a tensile stress of 3.0 MPa in contrast with the tensile stress of 1.5 MPa of L-PVA-ABPBI membrane. The elongation at break value of the crosslinked membrane reduces significantly compared with linear one (i.e., 30 % and 180 %, respectively).

3.4 Swelling, water sorption and KOH doping level

Table 2 shows the swelling results for membranes soaked for 7 days in 15 wt. % KOH at 25 °C. The volume swelling varies between 80 % and 95 % for all studied membranes. However, a different thickness and length swelling behaviour was observed compared the PBI-based membranes (L-PVA-PBI 4:1 and C-PVA-PBI 4:1) and ABPBI based membranes (L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 and C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1). The thickness of the PBI-based membranes increased 48-50 %, and the thickness of ABPBI membranes increased by only 14-18 % after doping in 15 wt. % KOH. However, the length of the PBI-based membranes increased 6-9 % compared to 25-27 % for the ABPBI-based membranes. The anisotropic swelling behaviour in the PBI membranes (i.e., swelling ratio in the thickness direction larger than that in the length/width directions) was reported by Aili et al. [20] and Zeng et al. [19]. The excessive and perhaps uneven swelling experienced by linear and crosslinked PVA-PBI membranes is most likely due to the molecular structure of this membranes, which compromises its stability as demonstrated by the results in section 3.3, and this behaviour could be reflected in the water electrolysis performance measurements. The effect of this characteristic will be evaluated below.

Table 2: Swelling behaviour of 15 wt. % KOH-doped membranes.

Membrane	Volume swelling / %	Thickness swelling / %	Length swelling / %
L-PVA-PBI 4:1	80 ± 5	48 ± 4	9 ± 1
L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1	83 ± 3	18 ± 7	25 ± 5
C-PVA-PBI 4:1 - 0.5 vol. % GA	95 ± 11	50 ± 5	6 ± 3

C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 - 0.5 vol. % GA	84 ± 12	14 ± 8	27 ± 6
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The increase in the volume after doping in the PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes was higher than that of pure polybenzimidazole membranes. Aili et al. [17] obtained a 64 % volume increase in linear PBI. This value is comparable to the 50 % increase reported by Diaz et al. [18] in L-ABPBI and C-ABPBI. The length and thickness increases were higher in the PBI membranes than in the L-ABPBI and C-ABPBI membranes (10 % and 17 % for thickness and length swelling, respectively [18]). However, this increase is still moderate, except for the increase in the thickness of the PBI-based membranes.

Considering that the anisotropic swelling observed (Table 2), can be disadvantageous during cell assembly, particularly the excessive swelling in area direction shown by L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI membranes, cell assembly tests were performed. At time zero, the membrane sample was extracted from the doping solution, placed between the two cell seals, and exposed to environmental conditions for one hour. During this time, the membrane had no contact with the KOH solution, simulating the cell assembly time interval. After 1 h, the membrane sample was immersed in the doping solution during 1.5 h, and then extracted, in order to check if it recover its initial state ($t = 0$). Images obtained at time zero, 10 min, 30 min, 45 min and 1 h and 2.5 h are shown at Figure S5.

Figure S5 shows that all the membranes keep their dimensions unaffected if the assembly period don't exceed 30 min. At 45 min it can be observed in all the membranes shrinking and swelling zones that will cause inadequate contact between membrane, seals and electrodes.

The KOH solution acts as a plasticizer, so, when the membrane is immersed again in the doping solution, it recovers its initial state. This means that if 30 min were not enough to complete the cell assembly, it is possible to recover the membrane by simple immersion in the doping solution.

The water and KOH uptake were determined for linear and crosslinked PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes after impregnation in KOH 15 wt. %. The results are shown in Table 3 and Figure 6.

Table 3: Polymer, water and KOH contents of 15 wt. % KOH-doped membranes.

Membrane	Polymer / %	KOH / %	H ₂ O / %
L-PVA-PBI 4:1	49 ± 2	1 ± 0.5	50 ± 2
L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1	30 ± 7	1 ± 0.5	69 ± 7
C-PVA-PBI 4:1 - 0.5 vol. % GA	73 ± 6	5 ± 0.5	22 ± 6
C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 - 0.5 vol. % GA	25 ± 4	8 ± 0.5	67 ± 4

In L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-ABPBI, the water uptake was 50 % and 69 %, respectively. The same membranes crosslinked with GA 0.5 % exhibited a decrease in the water uptake for C-PVA-PBI but not for C-PVA-ABPBI (see Figure 6), which retains a water uptake 67 %. The reduction in the water uptake in the C-PVA-PBI membrane may be related to the sharp consumption of OH⁻ groups from PVA, as observed in Figure 4b, which affects the hydrophilicity of the membrane as noted in section 3.2.

The KOH uptake can be divided into two contributions as described by H. Hou [13]. The first contribution is related to the acid–base reaction between the acid sites of the polybenzimidazole membranes and KOH to afford potassium polybenzimidazolate salt and water, and the second contribution is related to KOH entering the membrane structure, which is responsible for the OH⁻ transport within the membrane. However, the order of the steps is not important because free KOH is available without completing the total reaction with the acidic sites of the polybenzimidazole membranes.

The low KOH content of the L-PVA-PBI 4:1 and L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 linear membranes may be due to a calculation error. If polymer loss occurred during the doping stage, the calculated KOH uptake (based on the initial polymer weight) would be affected. However, the calculated water uptake (based on the weight difference between doped and dried membrane) would not be affected. This polymer loss may also be due to the structural change observed in the SEM analysis of the L-PVA-PBI membranes.

Differences were observed between the weight of de-doped, washed and dried samples and the weight of the initial dry sample (w_0); linear membranes (8-13 wt. % loss) and crosslinked membranes (~1 wt. % loss). As it was pointed out in section 2.6, in order to determine if this loss occurs during doping, IR spectroscopy was employed using the conditions described in section

2.6. Signals related to PVA were not observed. However, this is not enough to assess that no polymer loss occurs during doping. The absence of PVA signals can be due to limitations related with the detection limit of the IR spectroscopy equipment (10^{-6} mol l^{-1}) or degradation of PVA to lower molecular weight species with different absorption patterns.

Unfortunately, the amount of polymer loss that occurs during the doping stage and washing procedure cannot be distinguished.

Figure 6: Water (black) and KOH (red) uptake for the synthesized membranes.

3.5 Ionic conductivity (IC)

The ionic conductivities of linear and crosslinked PVA-PBI and PVA-ABPBI membranes doped in 15 wt. % KOH in a temperature range from 25 °C to 90 °C are shown in Figure 7 a). The L-PVA-PBI and L-PVA-ABPBI membranes exhibit ionic conductivities of 40 to 70 $mS \cdot cm^{-1}$, and

the conductivities of L-PVA-PBI were slightly higher than those of L-PVA-ABPBI, especially in the 60 and 90 °C range.

The C-PVA-PBI conductivities decreased to values less than 1 mS·cm⁻¹ at a 0.5 vol. % GA concentration in the reaction solution. For the C-PVA-ABPBI membranes, the membranes crosslinked at 0.5 vol. % GA exhibited conductivities ranging from 25 to 55 mS·cm⁻¹, and these values are only slightly lower than those of L-PVA-ABPBI. In addition, the conductivity in membranes crosslinked at 1 vol. % GA decreased. The C-PVA-PBI membranes and C-PVA-ABPBI membranes crosslinked at GA concentration higher than 0.5 vol. % in the reaction solution exhibited an unacceptable ionic conductivity for the application considered in this study and are not further characterized. C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 crosslinked with at 0.5 vol. % GA are referred to as C-PVA-ABPBI in subsequent sections.

The ionic conductivity of all PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes significantly increased with increasing temperature (25 °C – 90 °C) due to the increased mobility of the OH⁻ species within the polymeric membrane. The ionic conductivity was due to the KOH included in the membranes. The transport mechanism in the anion-exchange membranes is dependent on the relative humidity and temperature similar to the proton transport in Nafion[®] membranes [27,28]. In the Grotthuss mechanism, diffusion and convection are considered dominant transport mechanisms for OH⁻ transport through the membrane [5,29]. OH⁻ can diffuse via the hydrogen-bonded network of water molecules and the formation/dissociation of covalent bonds combined with a diffusion/migration transport process (vehicular mechanism). Insights into the activation energy of the OH⁻ conduction process can be extracted from the relationship between the conductivity (σ) and temperature by fitting the data to the Arrhenius expression (2):

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (2)$$

where E_a is the activation energy for electrical conduction, σ_0 is the maximum electrical conductivity (supposed at infinite temperature), and R is the gas constant.

The studied membranes exhibited similar relationships between the temperature and conductivity (see Figure 7 b), which indicated similar ionic conduction mechanisms. A linear relationship was obtained for the plot of \ln conductivity as a function of the inverse temperature. The activation energies for the L-PVA-ABPBI, L-PVA-PBI and C- PVA-ABPBI membranes are 6.3, 4.0 and 4.9 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively, which fall in the range of values that have been obtained for other alkaline membranes. Therefore, the crosslinked PVA/poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) membranes that were pre-treated with $1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ KOH have E_a values of 8–10 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ [30], and the PVA/sodium alginate membranes treated with 40 wt. % KOH have 7–40 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ [31]. However, other alkaline membranes including the PBI membranes impregnated in 4 mol l^{-1} KOH (22–23 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) [32] and ABPBI membranes doped in $1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ NaOH (13.6–14.2 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) [33] possess higher E_a values.

In agreement with the determined E_a values, several OH⁻ mechanisms for hydroxyl transport, such as the Grotthuss mechanism, surface site hopping, diffusion and convection via permeation and osmotic drag, may occur. The obtained activation energies were similar for all PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes, even the crosslinked ones. This result indicates that the crosslinking process does not affect the mechanism of hydroxyl transport within the membranes. Finally, all membranes exhibited conductivity values higher than $10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, which is considered the limit for an acceptable polymer electrolyte membrane [31].

In addition, the ionic conductivity (IC) results for L-PVA-PBI, L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI doped in 30 wt. % KOH are shown in Figure 7 c). The ICs values for the C-PVA-ABPBI membranes are higher than those of the linear PVA-PBI and PVA-ABPBI membranes, which may be due to improved resistance of the crosslinked membranes to chemical degradation compared to that of the linear ones. In addition, a particular molecular structure may allow for a higher KOH penetration capacity in the polymer matrix. The comparison between the conductivity values of C-PVA-PBI doped in 15 or 30 wt. % KOH indicates that a higher KOH concentration results in a higher conductivity value. This result may be due to this membrane not being completely doped in the 15 wt. % KOH solution.

The ionic conductivities measured in this study at temperatures near 90 °C with a 30 wt. % KOH doping solution were similar to those of linear ($90 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) and crosslinked ($60 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) PBI

membranes measured by Aili et al. [17] and Jheng et al. [34], who reported exhibit ionic conductivity values of $96 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ for linear PBI under the same conditions. Furthermore, our crosslinked membranes doped at $\approx 15 \text{ wt. \% KOH}$ exhibited IC values higher than that reported by Jheng et al. [34] for L-PBI doped at the same KOH concentration.

When doped in 15 wt. \% KOH , crosslinked membranes exhibited a lower conductivity than linear membranes. Their structures most likely allow for less OH^- mobility. In the C-PVA-PBI membranes, the substantial decrease in the conductivity may be due to the large decrease in water uptake that is related to the compact microstructure of this membrane as well as the consumption of pendant OH^- from PVA, which enhances the hydrophilicity as mentioned in section 3.2. Water molecules facilitate the Grotthuss mechanism. According to Merle et al. [5], the assumption that the Grotthuss mechanism is primarily responsible for hydroxide transport through the AEM is supported by the Grotthuss behaviour exhibited by hydroxide in aqueous solutions (i.e., OH^- diffuses through the H-bonded network of H_2O molecules through the formation/cleavage of covalent bonds). When doped in 30 wt. \% KOH , the C-PVA-ABPBI membrane exhibited the best conductivity, which is most likely related to the increase in the KOH uptake.

Figure 7: a) Ionic conductivity of membranes doped in 15 wt. % KOH: L-PVA-PBI; L-PVA-ABPBI; C-PVA-ABPBI (0.5 and 1 vol. % GA) and C-PVA-PBI (0.5 vol. % GA) b) Arrhenius plot for membranes doped in 15 wt. % KOH: L-PVA-PBI; L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI (0.5 vol. % GA) c) Ionic conductivity of membranes doped in 30 wt. % KOH: L-PVA-PBI, L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI (0.5 vol. % GA).

3.6 Alkaline water electrolysis

The experiment was performed by testing the PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes under LAWE conditions. A single-cell electrolyser with a zero gap configuration, as described in section 2.3, was fed with a 15 wt. % KOH aqueous solution at 50 °C and 70 °C. The I/E polarization curves obtained for the L-PVA-PBI, L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI membranes are shown in Figure 8 a). In a previous study [18], we demonstrated that the WE short-term performance of our linear and benzoxazine-crosslinked ABPBI membranes was better than that of the commercial Zirfon diaphragm under the applied conditions. The best performance was observed for C-ABPBI operating with 15 wt. % KOH at 70 °C, and this performance is comparable to that of industrial units, which are typically operated with 6–7 M KOH and 80-90 °C.

The results in Table 4 indicate that the performance of the L-PVA-PBI membranes is similar to those of the L-ABPBI and C-ABPBI membranes, and the performance of L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI was superior to that of ABPBI (2-3 M KOH, 50 °C) [18]. These results are in agreement with the conductivity results shown in Figure 7 a).

The performance of C-PVA-ABPBI is superior to that of the commercial porous Zirfon® diaphragm, 2.5 times higher than that of the C-ABPBI membranes (3 M KOH, 70 °C) and comparable to industrial units (6–7 M KOH, 80-90 °C) [18]. Furthermore, the performance of all the studied PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes at 15 wt. % KOH and 50 °C was superior to that of the Zirfon® diaphragm tested using the typical conditions for LAWE commercial units (30 wt. %, 80 °C) [21], which is a very important result. A membrane that allows us to achieve LAWE performances under mild conditions comparable to that of LAWE units with concentrated KOH at high temperatures is advantageous for preventing material corrosion and maintaining long-term membrane stability, as highlighted by Aili et al. [35]. This group demonstrated that L-PBI is stable for up to 200 days in 5 wt. % KOH at 88 °C but degrades at higher KOH concentrations.

As expected, the PVA-polybenzimidazole membrane performance improved by increasing the electrolyser operational temperature to 70 °C. In Figure 8 a), the C-PVA-ABPBI throughput

significantly improved and reached values of $360 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.9 V , even at 15 wt. \% KOH . To the best of our knowledge, this is currently the most promising result for a zero gap electrolyser. The measurement equipment has a safety current limit of $500 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. Therefore, the electric current cuts off at this limit.

Figure 8: a) LAWE load curves for membranes in 15 wt.% KOH at 50 °C and 70 °C: L-PVA-PBI 4:1; L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 and C-PVA-ABPBI (0.5 vol. % GA) 4:1. b) Chronopotentiometric curves for membranes in 15 wt.% KOH at 50 °C and 70 °C, $i = 200 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$: L-PVA-PBI 4:1; L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1 and C-PVA-ABPBI (0.5 vol. % GA) 4:1

Finally, the chronopotentiometric curves for the L-PVA-PBI, L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI membranes (15 wt. % KOH, 50 °C and 70 °C, $i = 200 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) are shown in Figure 8 b). The results are consistent with the performance exhibited by the linear sweep voltammetry curves (Figure 8 a), and the best outcomes were achieved by the C-PVA-ABPBI membrane at both working temperatures. In addition, the L-PVA-PBI membrane requires an additional 20 °C to achieve the same performance as that of C-PVA-ABPBI at 50 °C.

Table 4: Performance of laboratory electrolysis cell tested with circulating 15 wt. % KOH and different anion-exchange membranes.

Membrane	Temperature (°C)	Current density ($\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) at cell voltage 2 V
L-PVA-PBI 4:1	50	180
L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1	50	220
C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1	50	450*
L-PVA-PBI 4:1	70	430*
L-PVA-ABPBI 4:1	70	290
C-PVA-ABPBI 4:1	70	900*
Zirfon [®] [18]	50	140
Zirfon [®] [21]	80	~160**
L-ABPBI [18]	50	180
C-ABPBI [18]	50	160
L-ABPBI [18]	70	280
C-ABPBI [18]	70	335

* Extrapolated value

** 30 wt. % KOH

4. Conclusions

PVA:polybenzimidazole membranes (i.e., PVA-PBI and PVA-ABPBI) with compositions varying from 2:1 to 8:1 were prepared and tested in an alkaline water electrolysis cell.

Membranes with a PVA:polybenzimidazole ratio of 4:1 exhibited the best electrochemical performance.

To improve the membrane stability, PVA in the membranes was crosslinked by immersion in acetone solutions with various glutaraldehyde compositions. Membranes crosslinked by immersion in a reaction solution containing GA > 0.5 vol. % exhibited conductivities that were lower than $1 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, and therefore, only membranes crosslinked with GA = 0.5 vol. % were considered in this study.

Ionic conductivities up to $75 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were achieved by linear PVA-PBI and PVA-ABPBI membranes doped in 15 wt. % KOH, and crosslinked PVA-ABPBI membranes exhibited ionic conductivities up to $55 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at the same temperature and doping concentration. C-PVA-PBI membranes exhibited conductivities lower than $1 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$. C-PVA-ABPBI membranes exhibited high ionic conductivities ($90 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ when doped with 30 wt. % KOH, which is similar to that of linear PBI membranes [17,34].

All membranes exhibited a similar behaviour for water and KOH uptake, except for the thickness increase in PBI-based membranes. The thermooxidative stability of the linear and crosslinked membranes was satisfactory, with a decomposition temperature between 300 and $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The short-term WE performances of L-PVA-PBI, L-PVA-ABPBI and C-PVA-ABPBI were better than that of a standard Zirfon membrane separator. C-PVA-ABPBI exhibited the best performance at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 15 wt. % KOH. This result is comparable to that of industrial units operating at KOH concentrations of 6–7 M and 80 – $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Electrolysis cells that work at low KOH concentrations and temperatures are advantageous to ensure the long-term stability of materials in the final application. The durability of PVA-polybenzimidazole membranes under LAWE conditions will be further studied in the future.

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Highlights

Membranes based on polybenzimidazole / crosslinked polyvinyl alcohol were prepared
 The best membrane composition was selected for its electrolyzer performance
 High ionic conductivity was attained compared with doped polybenzimidazole membranes
 Electrolyzer performance was 2.5 times better than with pure polybenzimidazole

Graphical abstract

